

The role of perfectionism in enhancing job performance in İzmir destination hotels

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Abstract

Perfectionism is the behavior of people who set goals that are difficult to achieve in order to be perfect, to reach perfection and to exhibit high performance. Job performance, on the other hand, is the behavior of employees in a business in accordance with the purpose of the business while fulfilling their duties. Hotel businesses are labor-intensive businesses and the human element is of great importance. Job performance is affected by factors such as personality traits and behaviors of employees. Therefore, it is thought that perfectionism, which is known as a personality trait, may affect the job performance levels of employees. Accordingly, the purpose of this study is to examine the relationship between perfectionism perceptions of hotel employees and their job performance. In obtaining the research data, a questionnaire was used as a data collection tool. Convenience sampling method was used in the study and the population of the study consists of employees working in four and five star hotels in İzmir. The data obtained were analyzed with SPSS and AMOS programs. According to the results of the analysis, there is a significant relationship between perfectionism perception and job performance. In addition, it was concluded that perfectionism perception has a positive effect on job performance. According to this result, positive developments in employees' perceptions of perfectionism will positively affect their job performance levels.

Keywords: Perfectionism, Job Performance, Hotel, İzmir

1. Introduction

Today, globalization and developments in many fields are important for businesses to survive and gain competitive advantage. In the increasingly competitive environment of the tourism sector, the effective management and marketing of a destination has become more and more important. Attracting visitors to destinations is directly linked to the existence of businesses, the products they produce and the services they offer. The human element has become increasingly important in businesses trying to survive and gain competitive advantage. Due to the fact that hotel businesses are in the service sector and have labor-intensive characteristics, they need the human element in order to adapt to today's conditions. Personality traits are an important factor in the success of employees in hotel businesses and their ability to work efficiently and in accordance with professional principles, and there is an interaction between business-level expectations and personality traits in shaping their behaviors (Ünal, 2002; Yelboğa, 2006). Factors such as rewarding and excellence model, which

are important in business life, ensure the emergence of positive behaviors such as success, motivation and productivity when they are compatible with employees' expectations and personality traits (Eren & Küçükaltan, 2017).

Much research has been conducted on the role of perfectionism by researchers in various psychological disciplines. However, the role of perfectionism in business life remains largely unclear. The concept of perfectionism has been accepted as a personality trait as a result of research and is defined in the literature as "striving for perfection, setting extremely high standards for high performance". The concept of perfectionism, which was first subjected to research in the 1950s, was first focused on its negative traits and treated as a single dimension. In the following years, both its negative and positive aspects were emphasized and it was analyzed as multidimensional. According to the definitions of perfectionism in the literature, it is noteworthy that it is effective on individuals' performance and behaviors. Therefore, individuals with high perfectionism perception fulfill their duties

more carefully and confidently. Accordingly, perfectionism in business life affects the productivity, performance and motivation of employees (Harari, Steed, Swider, & Breidenthal, 2018). The fact that employee performance has a significant impact on the success of businesses increases the importance of the human element in hotel businesses in the service sector. From this point of view, the effect of perfectionism in business life in the service sector, where the human element is extremely important, is an issue that should be evaluated in terms of employees and managers.

The main purpose of the study is to examine the effect of perfectionism perception on job performance of employees in four and five star hotels in Izmir. In this direction, a study was designed on 393 hotel employees, the data obtained were analyzed and the research findings were presented. When the literature is examined, the concept of perfectionism has been the subject of many studies in different psychology disciplines and has recently been included in new studies in various branches. However, the effect of perfectionism on business life remains unclear. Therefore, due to the lack of studies addressing the relationship between perfectionism and job performance, it is thought that the research will contribute to the literature and will benefit the sector by making important suggestions.

2. Perfectionism

When we consider human beings as a biological being, their personality traits are shaped according to social and cultural influences, the situation they are in and their biological distinction. One of these personality traits is perfectionism (Tuncer & Voltan Acar, 2006). Adler, one of the leading researchers in the field, defines perfectionism as "an effort to avoid deficiency" or "an effort for superiority". Adler argued that perfectionism emerges from the social environment and is a necessity in the individual's life (Adler, 2012). Burns defined perfectionism as "all or nothing" and according to him, if an individual fails to achieve perfection in his/her work, he/she is unsuccessful, but if he/she achieves his/her goal and shows an excellent performance, he/she aims to do the best by asking for more (Burns, 2002). According to Hewitt and Flett (1991), perfectionism is the effort to strive for perfection or to reach and maintain unattainable standards (cited in Uz Baş, 2010: 128).

Perfectionism was first considered as a personality disorder in the 1950s, focusing on the individual himself/herself, and only the negative aspects were examined and handled as one-dimensional. In the 1970s, on the other hand, perfectionism was considered as multidimensional by developing a one-dimensional perspective, considering that

perfectionism is not only caused by itself, the environment in which the individual is also effective and that it also has positive aspects (Bayram, 2016: 19).

According to Adler (2004), who handles perfectionism as a single dimension with positive and negative dimensions, when a person uses his/her drive for superiority not only for his/her own purposes but also for the benefit of the society, he/she is characterized as a positive perfectionist; on the other hand, people who do not benefit the society and act in line with the aim of being superior to other people are characterized as negative perfectionists (Adler, 2012; Altun & Yazıcı, 2010: 535). Asby, Rice, and Slaney (1998), on the other hand, considered perfectionism as compatible and incompatible in a single dimension. According to them, congruent perfectionists are those who make a lot of effort to achieve their goals in line with their high standards, act in a planned manner and do not engage in procrastination behavior; maladaptive perfectionists are those who set high goals for themselves and have difficulty in achieving their goals, worry about making mistakes and are prone to procrastination behavior (Ashby, Rice, & Slaney, 1998; Slaney, Rice, Mobley, Trippi, & Ashby, 2001). Frost, Marten, Lahart, and Rosenblate (1990), on the other hand, considered perfectionism, which has many features, as the most striking feature of perfectionism, as keeping the performance standards of the individual at an extremely high level in order to achieve success. According to Frost and colleagues, the individual evaluates himself negatively when he fails to reach these high performance standards (Frost, Marten, Lahart, & Rosenblate, 1990: 450).

Table 1. Unidimensional Perfectionism Approaches

Researchers	Dimensions Of Excellence
Roedel, 1984; Adler, 2004; Owens and Slade, 2008	1. Positive (Healthy) 2. Negative (Unhealthy)
Hamachek, 1978	1. Normal 2. Neurotic
Rice, Slaney and Asby, 1996	1. Adaptive 2. Maladaptive
Siegle and Schuler, 2000	1. Internal 2. External

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Based on the literature review, the researchers who examined perfectionism as unidimensional made a common statement that perfectionist individuals set high standards for themselves and create an effect only on themselves. However, later on, by taking into account not only the individual himself/herself but also his/her environment, it is seen in the literature that perfectionism is examined multidimensionally as well as unidimensionally. Therefore, the concept of perfectionism, which was initially examined as one-dimensional, started to be examined multidimensionally by researchers such as Frost,

Marten, Lahart, Rosenblate, Hewitt and Flett as a result of the researches (Gürbüzkol, 2018: 13).

Table 2. Multidimensional Approaches to Perfectionism

Researchers	Dimensions Of Excellence
Frost, Marten, Lahart, Rosenblate, 1990	Worry about making mistakes High personal standards High parental expectations 4.Suspicion of behavior Order Parental criticism
Hewin and Flett, 1991	1.Self-oriented perfectionism 2.Other-oriented perfectionism 3.Socially oriented perfectionism

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Within the scope of this study, the perception of perfectionism is considered as multidimensional and the three-dimensional scale developed by Hewitt and Flett was used to measure the perception of perfectionism. Therefore, it would be appropriate to explain these three dimensions in detail. These three dimensions are self-oriented perfectionism, which involves setting unrealistic expectations for oneself, other-oriented perfectionism, which involves setting high standards for other people, and social-oriented perfectionism, which involves expecting unattainable things from others. These dimensions are explained as follows (Hewitt & Flett, 1991b): Self-oriented perfectionism: It includes behaviors such as setting extremely high standards for oneself that are difficult to achieve, evaluating oneself strictly according to the achievement of these standards, criticizing oneself and not accepting one's mistakes. In this case, the individual holds himself/herself responsible for the mistakes that occur. Self-punishment behavior is observed in self-oriented perfectionism. Other-oriented perfectionism: It is similar to self-oriented perfectionism, but the behavior is focused on other people, not on oneself (Hewitt & Flett, 1991a). This dimension includes the beliefs and expectations of the individual towards other people around him/her. Perfectionist individuals set unreasonable and unattainable standards for other people and evaluate their performances strictly by expecting them to be perfect. Socially oriented perfectionism: This dimension of perfectionism involves the individual's need to reach high standards and expectations set by the people he/she cares about in order to be approved by the social environment. The socially oriented perfectionist individual has the belief that other people expect standards that are difficult to achieve from him/her and that they will evaluate him/her strictly according to whether he/she is perfect or not. Individuals with a high perception of socially oriented perfectionism experience fear of being evaluated negatively by other people as they strive to

meet their expectations and desires (Hewitt & Flett, 1991a; 1991b).

3. Business Performance

The concept of performance is defined by Bingöl (1990) as "a concept that determines the completion of the task in line with the determined goal and the extent to which the result obtained from the result reaches the goal". Job performance, on the other hand, is defined by Barutçugil (2002) as "the result of the time and effort spent by employees in order to realize the objectives of the business". When the literature on job performance is examined, it is seen that job performance is a multidimensional concept. However, the literature mostly utilizes the "task performance" and "contextual performance" classifications proposed by Borman and Motowidlo (1997). This classification is based on the view that it is not enough to perform only the tasks required by the job, contextual performance actions are also important (Aktaş & Şimşek, 2014). Borman and Motowidlo (1997) examined job performance in two sub-dimensions as task performance and contextual performance. Task performance is defined as employees' fulfilling their duties in order to support the technical power of the business, while contextual performance is defined as behaviors that support social and organizational activities, taking into account the efficiency of the business and the work performed, and are outside of task performance (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997). Task performance is the performance dimension that consists of the activities in the job description and contributes to the technical structure of the organization, where the professional knowledge and mastery of the employee is effective, although it varies from job to job (Özdevecioğlu & Kanıgür, 2009). Contextual performance, which is equivalent to the concept of "organizational citizenship" in the literature, is defined as a set of behaviors that contribute to organizational effectiveness through their impact on the psychological, social and organizational context of the job (Impelman, 2007). Özdevecioğlu, Akın, Karaca, and İştahlı (2014) stated that only task performance is not enough in the competitive market and contextual performance should also be high, and employees should support the organization with behaviors that are not included in the official job description for the success of the organization (Özdevecioğlu et al., 2014).

4. The Relationship between Perfectionism and Job Performance

There are many studies in the literature that reveal the relationship between perfectionism and job performance. As a result of a study in which the effect of perfectionism perceptions of cooks working in chain hotels in Istanbul on job performance was measured; it was concluded that the dimensions of perfectionism had a significant effect on the contextual performance

of employees, but the effect of perfectionism towards others was negative. On the other hand, it was concluded that only the effect of other-oriented perfectionism variable on task performance was significant but at a low level, while there was no effect of self-oriented and social-oriented perfectionism variables on task performance (Eren, 2013). In Balçioğlu's (2019) study on public managers, it was found that there was a significant positive relationship between perceived perfectionism level and general performance. Hrabluik, Latham, and McCarthy (2012) concluded that general perfectionism is negatively related to performance in a sample of police officers. Günyaktı (2021) examined the effect of congruent and incongruent perfectionism perceptions of 347 white-collar employees working in different sectors on task performance and concluded that the effect of employees' congruent perfectionism perceptions on task performance is significant and positive.

Altun and Yazıcı (2010) examined the relationship between students' positive and negative perfectionism traits and their academic achievement. The research group consisted of 1100 students, 571 of whom were female and 529 of whom were male, studying in 19 different primary schools in Trabzon province. According to the findings of the study, there is a significant relationship between students' positive perfectionism levels and their academic achievement. The relationship between negative perfectionism level and academic achievement was found to be negative. Stoll, Lau, and Stoeber (2008) studied 112 athletes and examined the effect of perfectionism on athletes' performance. While some researchers defined perfectionism as a distinctive characteristic in athletes, others considered perfectionism as a negative characteristic that weakens performance. In this study, two aspects of perfectionism were examined: striving for perfection and showing negative reactions to imperfections. According to the findings of the study, it was concluded that striving for perfection during training was effective in showing higher performance in a new task. In addition, the reactions to flaws and mistakes did not negatively affect the performance of the athletes and led to an increase in their performance. As a result of these findings, it was found that perfectionism is generally not a negative trait that weakens the athlete's performance (Stoll, Lau, & Stoeber, 2008). Another study of 100 university students, which examined the relationship between task time, perfectionistic challenges and task performance, found that perfectionism has a positive relationship with task time and task performance. According to the other finding, accuracy and rigor of task performance are more important than speed for perfectionist students. In addition, task time was found to mediate between perfectionism and task

performance. As a result of these findings, it was concluded that perfectionist students perform better by spending more time than non-perfectionist students. The current findings also showed that perfectionism is associated with high performance (Stoeber, Chesterman, & Tarn, 2010). Kobori and Tanno (2005), who examined the negative and positive aspects of self-oriented perfectionism, observed that individuals with high self-oriented perfectionism set very high standards for themselves, first make mistakes and their performance is negatively affected, but then they overcome their failures and the performance of perfectionists is positively affected. Flett, Greene, and Hewitt (2004) examined the relationship between the dimensions of perfectionism and anxiety level and concluded that socially oriented perfectionist individuals show negative contextual performance behaviors along with behaviors such as not being open to evaluation and criticism by other employees, reacting and being anxious. In a study conducted on students, it was observed that the perception of socially oriented perfectionism has negative effects such as depression, anxiety and inadequacy (Lee, Haa, & Jue, 2019).

5. Research Methodology

Purpose and Importance of Research

Tourism differs from other sectors in the service sector in that it is labor intensive. The most important factor that determines the attitude of customers towards hotel businesses is the service they receive from the business. In this context, the basic basis of hotel management is based on the human factor (Şener, 2001). As in all businesses, providing a good service to customers in tourism businesses is related to the performance and behavior of employees. The interaction of service receivers and service providers, the perceptions of employees and the positive or negative results of their performance affect hotel businesses (Kozak, 2016; Ünlüönen & Şahin, 2011). Perfectionism, which is accepted as a personality trait as a result of the researches, is a trait that affects the performance level of individuals. Since perfectionism is a personality trait, it is possible for people to show an effect in all areas of their lives, including their business life. If perfectionism is not managed well in business life, negative situations such as stress and depression may be encountered. As a result, situations such as employees quitting their jobs, decreasing productivity and performance can create very negative consequences for businesses. At this point, it is important for managers to monitor employees well (Eren, 2013).

The purpose of the study is to determine the effect of perfectionism perception on job performance of

employees working in 4 and 5 star hotels operating in Izmir province. Since there is a limited number of studies in literature explaining the relationship between perfectionism and job performance in the tourism sector, it can be said that this study can contribute to the literature.

Measurement Tools and Data Collection

Data were collected through a questionnaire. In the first part of the questionnaire form, there are 9 questions about demographic variables (gender, marital status, age, etc.). In the second part, there are 45 statements regarding the perfectionism scale and in the third part, there are 25 statements regarding the job performance scale. "Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale" developed by Hewitt and Flett (1990) and adapted into Turkish by Oral (1999) was used to measure the perfectionism perception of employees. This scale consists of three dimensions: self-oriented perfectionism, other-oriented perfectionism and social-oriented perfectionism. An example of the self-oriented perfectionism dimension is the statement "When I work on a task, I cannot relax until it is perfect.", an example of the other-oriented perfectionism dimension is the statement "I do not criticize others for giving up easily.", and an example of the socially oriented perfectionism dimension is the statement "I have difficulty in meeting others' expectations of me."

The job performance scale applied to measure the job performance of hotel employees was developed by Goodman and Syvanteck (1999). The scale consists of two dimensions, task performance and contextual

performance, and includes 25 statements. While 16 statements of the scale measure contextual performance, 9 statements measure task performance (Polatçı, 2011). Since the 4th, 8th and 10th statements in the scale are reverse expressions, these statements were reverse coded and included in the analysis. The scales were used as a 5-point Likert-type scale. Accordingly, the scales included options ranging from the most negative to the most positive, with 1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree.

Research Model and Hypotheses

The model and research hypotheses showing the relationship between the variables within the scope of the research are presented below.

- **Main hypothesis:**
Perfectionism perception has a significant effect on job performance.

H1: Employees' self-perceptions of perfectionism have a significant effect on their contextual performance.

H1: There is a significant effect of employees' self-perceptions of perfectionism on their task performance.

H1 : There is a significant effect of employees' perceptions of perfectionism towards others on their contextual performance.

H1: Employees' perceptions of perfectionism towards others have a significant effect on their task performance.

Figure 1. Research Model

H1: Employees' perceptions of socially oriented perfectionism have a significant effect on their contextual performance.

H1: Employees' perceptions of socially oriented perfectionism have a significant effect on their task performance.

Research Population and Sample

The population of the study consists of the employees of 4 and 5 star hotel establishments in Izmir province and convenience sampling was used. A total of 27 hotel establishments, including 3 five- star hotel establishments and 24 four-star hotel establishments, were surveyed. According to the information obtained from the four and five star hotel establishments in the

city center of Izmir, which constitute the research population, it was determined that there were an average of 1170 employees. It was possible to reach 402 employees who voluntarily agreed to participate in the survey. Nine of these questionnaires were not evaluated because they were incomplete or filled out in a way that was not suitable for data analysis. As a result, 393 questionnaires were evaluated and the data were analyzed.

6. Statistical Analyses and Results

Findings Regarding the Demographic Information of the Participants

When the distribution of the employees according to their demographic characteristics is examined; 61,1% of them are male, 50,6% of them are single, 43,5% of

Table 3. Distribution of Employees According to Demographic Characteristics

Demographic	Group	n	%
Gender	Woman	153	38,9
	Male	240	61,1
	Total	393	100,0
Marital Status	Married	194	49,4
	Single	199	50,6
	Total	393	100,0
Age	20 years and younger	20	5,1
	21-30 years old	171	43,5
	31-40 years old	124	31,6
	41-50 years old	47	12,0
	51 years and over	31	7,9
Total	393	100,0	
Education Status	Primary education	5	1,3
	High School	81	20,6
	Associate Degree	92	23,4
	License	191	48,6
	Master's Degree	18	4,6
	PhD	6	1,5
Total	393	100,0	
Income Status	1404 TL and below	4	1,0
	1405-2000 TL	5	1,3
	2001-3000 TL	58	14,8
	3001-4000 TL	126	32,1
	4001 TL and above	200	50,9
Total	393	100,0	
Duration of Employment in the Sector	Less than 1 year	43	10,9
	1-3 years	97	24,7
	4-6 years	87	22,1
	7-9 years	65	16,5
	10 years and above	101	25,7
Total	393	100,0	
Working Time at the Hotel	Less than 1 year	96	24,4
	1-3 years	138	35,1
	4-6 years	83	21,1
	7-9 years	36	9,2
	10 years and above	40	10,2
Total	393	100,0	
Education in Tourism	Yes	268	68,2
	No.	125	31,8
	Total	393	100,0
Department Worked in	Front Office	59	15,0
	Housekeeping	58	14,8
	Food and Beverage Department	93	23,7
	Security	25	6,4
	Accounting	32	8,1
	Sales Marketing	39	9,9
	Public Relations	32	8,1
	Human Resources	24	6,1
	Purchasing	10	2,5
	Other	21	5,3
	Total	393	100,0

Source: Elaborated by Authors

them are 21-30 years old, 48,6% of them are undergraduate graduates, 50,9% of them have a monthly income of 4001 TL and above. When the distribution of the employees according to their working time in the sector is analyzed; 25,7% of them have been working for 10 years or more, and when the distribution of the employees according to their working time in the hotel is analyzed; 35,1% of them have been working for 1-3 years. When the distribution of the employees according to their education in the field of tourism was analyzed, it was determined that 68.2% of them received education in the field of tourism, and when the distribution of the employees according to the department they work in was analyzed, it was determined that 23.7% of them work in the food and beverage department.

Research Validity and Reliability

Cronbach's alpha coefficient (α) was used to measure the reliability of the data obtained in the study. Cronbach's alpha, which provides information about how consistent the statements in the scale are with

each other and to what extent they represent the concept in question, is the most common method used to measure reliability (Gürbüz & Şahin, 2016). According to the alpha coefficient, the reliability values of the scale are as follows (Lorcu, 2015): $0 \leq a < 0.40$ means that the scale is not reliable. $0.40 \leq a < 0.60$ means that the scale has low reliability. $0.60 \leq a < 0.80$ means that the scale is highly reliable. $0.80 \leq a < 1$ means that the scale is highly reliable.

In the first stage of the study analysis, skewness and kurtosis values were examined to determine whether the data were normally distributed. Shao (2002) stated that skewness and kurtosis values between -3 and 3 are appropriate. When the items were examined, it was determined that the values were within this range and showed multiple normal distribution. After determining the skewness and kurtosis values, validity and reliability analyses were conducted. The skewness and kurtosis values for the variables and their sub-dimensions are presented in Table 3.2. After the normality analysis, confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to test the accuracy of the relationship

Table 4: Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale Factor Analysis

Factors/Agents	Factor Loadings DFA	Skewness	kurtosis
Perfectionism			
Self-Oriented Perfectionism			
KYM1	,753	-1,278	,935
KYM2	,824	-,963	-,093
KYM5	,859	-1,176	,472
KYM6	,896	-,823	-,416
KYM7	,890	-1,235	,670
KYM8	,783	-,432	-1,062
KYM9	,734	-,927	-,176
KYM10	,889	-,888	-,223
KYM11	,846	-,310	1,193
KYM14	,802	-,570	-,944
KYM15	,803	-1,061	,331
Other-Oriented Perfectionism			
BYM1	,653	-,087	-1,277
BYM2	,731	,614	-,798
BYM3	,765	-,231	-1,186
BYM5	,737	-,676	-,636
BYM7	,780	-,312	-1,053
BYM9	,838	-,310	-1,076
BYM13	,564	,355	-,982
BYM14	,660	-,641	-,602
BYM15	,757	-,264	-1,173
Socially Oriented Perfectionism			
SOM3	,772	-1,065	,131
SOM4	,664	-,178	-1,234
SOM5	,810	-1,083	,377
SOM7	,509	,283	-1,213
SOM9	,800	-,896	-,076
SOM10	,687	-,317	-,864
SOM11	,750	-,855	-,393
SOM13	,783	-,285	-1,113
SOM14	,835	-,714	-,518

Source: Elaborated by Authors

between the variables previously analyzed (Hewitt, Flett, Turnbull, & Mikail, 1991) and to determine the suitability of the scale used for the research sample. Statements 3, 4, 12, and 13 belonging to the self-oriented perfectionism dimension, 4, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12 belonging to the others-oriented sub-

dimension, and 1, 2, 6, 8, 12, and 15 belonging to the socially oriented perfectionism sub-dimension with factor loadings below 0.50 were excluded from the analysis. As seen in Table 4, the factor loadings of the scale are between 0.509 and 0.896. While reporting the results of the analysis, the statements were coded as SDM (self-oriented perfectionism), SOM (other-oriented perfectionism) and SOM (socially oriented perfectionism). The factor loadings obtained as a result of CFA for the perfectionism scale are presented in Table 4.

Analysis Results Regarding the Scales

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was found to be 0.96 in the principal components factor analysis applied to the scale consisting of 25 items to measure the level of traditionalism-modernity of tourist guides. Accordingly, it is possible to say that the data set is suitable for factor analysis. As a result of the analysis conducted in the study, Barlett's test was significant as ,000 ($\chi^2= 12624,506$; $p<0.01$). The results of the principal components factor analysis applied to the scale for measuring the level of traditionalism-modernity of tourist guides using varimax rotation method are shown in Table 4. Accordingly, the variables to be included in the new scale were determined by considering the loading values in the scale consisting of 25 items. 16 items formed a 5-factor structure with eigenvalues above 1. These 5 factors explain 92.58% of the total variance of the scale consisting of 16 items. The results of the obtained scale are shown in Table 4.

In the reporting of confirmatory factor analysis, fit indices are examined. The fit index values for the perfectionism scale obtained as a result of CFA are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Fit Indices for the Multidimensional Perfectionism Scale

Compliance Measures	Good Compliance	Acceptable Compliance	Values	Conclusion
χ^2 / df	$0 \leq \chi^2 / df \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / df \leq 5$	3,42	Acceptable fit
RMSEA	$0 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.08 \leq RMSEA \leq 1.00$	0,79	Good fit
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0,90	Acceptable fit

Source: Hair et al. 1998; cited in. Varinli, Yaraş and Başalp, 2009; Kaplan, 2000; cited in. Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003.

The factorial structure of the perfectionism scale was tested using AMOS program. When the results of the goodness of fit values obtained as a result of CFA are examined, it is seen that the model is compatible with the data and acceptable (see Table 5). According to this result, it can be said that the data obtained are compatible with the theoretical structure of the perfectionism scale.

Table 6. Job Performance Scale Factor Analysis

Factors/Agents	Factor Loadings DFA	Skewness	kurtosis
Business Performance			
Contextual Performance			
BP1	,714	-1,120	,570
BP2	,812	-1,821	1,146
BP3	,708	-,762	-,453
BP5	,778	-1,532	2,348
BP7	,826	-1,487	2,093
BP9	,806	-1,467	1,706
BP11	,748	-1,396	1,289
BP12	,915	-1,704	2,090
BP13	,902	-1,612	2,649
BP14	,887	-1,665	2,466
BP15	,724	-,785	-,213
BP16	,683	-1,492	1,375
Task Performance			
GP1	,913	-1,563	2,324
GP2	,923	-1,681	2,656
GP3	,924	-1,486	2,121
GP4	,932	-1,760	2,094
GP5	,751	-,854	-,134
GP6	,826	-,961	,402
GP7	,861	-1,145	,977
GP8	,911	-1,724	2,800
GP9	,900	-1,757	2,159

Source: Elaborated by Authors

The kurtosis and skewness values of the job performance scale in Table 6 show that it is suitable for normal distribution. Statements 4, 6, 8 and 10 of the contextual performance sub-dimension, whose factor loadings were below 0.50, were removed from the job performance scale applied to CFA and analyzed. As seen in Table 3.4, the factor loadings of the scale are between 0.708 and 0.924. While reporting the analysis results, the statements were coded as BP (contextual performance) and GP (task performance). The fit index values obtained as a result of CFA of the job performance scale are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. Fit Indices for Job Performance Scale

Compliance Measures	Good Compliance	Acceptable Compliance	Values	Conclusion
χ^2 / df	$0 \leq \chi^2 / df \leq 2$	$2 \leq \chi^2 / df \leq 5$	4,53	Acceptable fit
RMSEA	$0 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.05$	$0.08 \leq RMSEA \leq 1.00$	0,95	Acceptable fit
CFI	$0.97 \leq CFI \leq 1.00$	$0.90 \leq CFI \leq 0.97$	0,93	Acceptable fit

Source: Hair et al. 1998; cited in. Varinli, Yaraş and Başalp, 2009;Kaplan, 2000; cited in. Schermelleh-Engel et al., 2003.

The factorial structure of the job performance scale was tested using AMOS program. When the results of the goodness of fit values obtained as a result of CFA are analyzed, it is seen that the model is compatible with the data and acceptable (see Table 7). According to this result, it can be said that the data obtained are compatible with the theoretical structure of the job performance scale. After confirmatory factor analysis, Cronbach's alpha reliability analysis was conducted to test the reliability of the scales.

Table 8. Reliability Analysis of Perfectionism Scale

Scale and Subscales	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Articles
Self-Oriented Perfectionism	0,958	11
Perfectionism	0,944	29
Socially Oriented Perfectionism	0,911	9
Other-Oriented Perfectionism	0,906	9

Source: Elaborated by Authors

Cronbach's Alpha values were analyzed to determine the internal consistency reliability of the perfectionism scale. The reliability coefficient of the perfectionism scale consisting of 29 statements was 0.944, the reliability coefficient of the self-oriented perfectionism sub-dimension consisting of 11 statements was 0.958, the reliability coefficient of the other-oriented perfectionism sub- dimension consisting of 9 statements was 0.906 and the reliability coefficient of the social-oriented perfectionism sub-dimension consisting of 9 statements was 0.911. In this case, the reliability of the general perfectionism scale and each sub-dimension is high.

Table 12. Correlation Analysis of Job Performance and Perfectionism Sub-Dimensions

Sub Dimensions	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Contextual Performance (1)	1	0,925*	0,985*	0,607*	0,231*	0,499*	0,584*
Task Performance(2)		1	0,976*	0,606*	0,226*	0,483*	0,576*
Business Performance(3)			1	0,618*	0,234*	0,501*	0,592*
Self-Oriented Perfectionism(4)				1	0,238*	0,788*	0,895*
Other-Oriented Perfectionism(5)					1	0,203*	0,581*
Socially Oriented Perfectionism(6)						1	0,857*
Perfectionism(7)							1

*p<0.05

Source: Elaborated by Authors

Table 9. Reliability Analysis of Job Performance Scale

Scale and Subscales	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Articles
Business Performance	0,977	21
Task Performance	0,969	9
Contextual Performance	0,952	12

Source: Elaborated by Authors

Cronbach's Alpha values were analyzed to determine the internal consistency reliability of the job performance scale. The reliability coefficient of the job performance scale consisting of 21 statements was 0.977, the reliability coefficient of the contextual performance sub-dimension consisting of 12 statements was 0.952 and the reliability coefficient of the task performance sub- dimension consisting of 9 statements was 0.969. In this case, the reliability of the overall job performance scale and each sub-dimension is high. Following the distribution, factor analysis and reliability analyses of the data, descriptive analyses were conducted and correlation analyses were performed for the scale dimensions.

Table 10. Descriptive Findings Related to Perfectionism Levels

Sub Dimensions	X	s.s.
Self-Oriented Perfectionism	3,85	1,01
Perfectionism	3,60	0,77
Socially Oriented Perfectionism	3,50	0,95
Other-Oriented Perfectionism	3,38	0,95

Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the descriptive findings of the perfectionism levels are analyzed, it is seen that the self- oriented perfectionism levels of the employees ($\bar{x}=3.85$) high, general perfectionism levels ($\bar{x}=3.60$) was found to be high. Socially oriented perfectionism levels ($\bar{x}=3.50$) and perfectionism towards others ($\bar{x}=3.38$) was found to be medium.

Table 11. Descriptive Findings on Job Performance Level

Sub Dimensions	X	s.s.
Task Performance	4,13	0,91
Business Performance	4,10	0,86
Contextual Performance	4,08	0,86

Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the descriptive findings of job performance levels are analyzed, task performance levels ($\bar{x}=4.13$) high, general job performance levels ($\bar{x}=4.10$) high and

contextual performance levels ($\bar{x}=4.08$) was found to be higher.

Correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationship between the variables, and according to the results of the correlation analysis, it can be said that there is a high level positive relationship between self-oriented perfectionism and contextual performance ($r=0,607$), a high level positive relationship between task performance ($r=0,606$), and a medium level positive relationship between perfectionism perception in general and job performance in general ($r=0,592$). There is a moderate positive relationship between socially oriented perfectionism, one of the sub-dimensions of perfectionism, and contextual performance ($r=0,499$) and task performance ($r=0,483$). It can be said that there is a low level positive relationship between perfectionism towards others and contextual performance ($r=0,231$) and task performance ($r=0,226$).

Table 13. The Effect of Perfectionism Perception on Job Performance Level

Variable	B	Standard Error	β	t	Sig.
Fixed	1,701	0,169	-	10,115	0,000*
Perfectionism	0,666	0,044	0,592	14,509	0,000*

* $p<0.05$
Adjusted R2 =0.348;
Durbin Watson= 1,939
Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the assumptions of regression analysis are analyzed, it is seen that the perception of perfectionism is effective on job performance. Within the findings obtained, it was determined that perfectionism perception explained 34.8% of the change in job performance level (adjusted R²

=0.348). According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), there is a positive and significant ($\beta=0.592$, $p=0.000$ $p<0.05$) relationship between perfectionism perception and job performance. In line with the findings, the main hypothesis is accepted.

Table 14. The Effect of Self-Perception of Perfectionism on Contextual Performance Level

Variable	B	Standard Error	β	T	Sig.
Fixed	2,094	0,136	-	15,355	0,000*
Self-Oriented Perfectionism	0,517	0,034	0,607	15,118	0,000*

* $p<0.05$
Adjusted R2 =0.367;
Durbin Watson= 1,877
Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the assumptions of regression analysis are analyzed, it is seen that self-perception of perfectionism is effective on contextual performance. Within the findings obtained, it was determined that self-perception of perfectionism explained 36.7% of the change in contextual performance level (adjusted R²

=0.367). According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), there is a positive and significant ($\beta=0.607$, $p=0.000$ $p<0.05$) relationship between self-perception of perfectionism and contextual performance. In line with the findings, H₁ is accepted.

Table 15. The Effect of Self-Oriented Perfectionism Perception on Task Performance Level

Variable	B	Standard Error	β	t	Sig.
Fixed	2,037	0,144	-	14,125	0,000*
Self-Oriented Perfectionism	0,545	0,036	0,606	15,061	0,000*

* $p<0.05$
Adjusted R2 =0.366;
Durbin Watson= 1,959
Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the assumptions of regression analysis are analyzed, it is seen that self-perception of perfectionism is effective on task performance. Within the findings obtained, it was determined that self-oriented perfectionism perception explained 36.6% of the change in task performance level (adjusted R² =0.366). According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), there is a positive and significant ($\beta=0.606$, $p=0.000$ $p<0.05$) relationship between self-perception of perfectionism and task performance. In line with the findings, H₂ is accepted.

Table 16. The Effect of Perception of Perfectionism Towards Others on Contextual Performance Level

Variable	B	Standard Error	β	T	Sig.
Fixed	3,378	0,157	-	21,548	0,000*
Other-Oriented Perfectionism	0,210	0,045	0,231	4,705	0,000*

* $p<0.05$
Adjusted R² =0.051;
Durbin Watson= 1,744
Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the assumptions of regression analysis are examined, it is seen that the perception of perfectionism towards others is effective on contextual performance. Within the findings obtained, it was determined that the perception of perfectionism towards others explained 5.1% of the change in contextual performance level (adjusted R² =0.051). According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), there is a positive and significant ($\beta=0.231$, $p=0.000$ $p<0.05$) relationship between the perception of perfectionism towards others and contextual performance. In line with the findings, H₃ is accepted.

Table 17. The Effect of Perception of Perfectionism Towards Others on Task Performance Level

Variable	B	Standard Error	β	t	Sig.
Fixed	3,405	0,166	-	20,539	0,000*
Other-Oriented Perfectionism	0,217	0,047	0,226	4,597	0,000*

*p<0.05

Adjusted R² =0.049;

Durbin Watson= 1,812

Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the assumptions of regression analysis are analyzed, it is seen that the perception of perfectionism towards others is effective on task performance. Within the findings obtained, it was determined that the perception of perfectionism towards others explained 4.9% of the change in task performance level (adjusted R² =0.049). According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), there is a positive and significant ($\beta=0.226$, p=0.000 p<0.05) relationship between the perception of perfectionism towards others and task performance. In line with the findings, H₄ is accepted.

Table 18. The Effect of Socially Oriented Perfectionism Perception on Contextual Performance Level

Variable	B	Standard Error	β	t	Sig.
Fixed	2,510	0,144	-	17,460	0,000*
Socially Oriented Perfectionism	0,450	0,040	0,499	11,380	0,000*

*p<0.05

Adjusted R² =0.249;

Durbin Watson= 1,995

Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the assumptions of regression analysis are analyzed, it is seen that socially oriented perfectionism perception is effective on contextual performance. Within the findings obtained, it was determined that the perception of socially oriented perfectionism explained 24.9% of the change in contextual performance level (adjusted R² =0.249). According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), there is a positive and significant ($\beta=0.499$, p=0.000 p<0.05) relationship between socially oriented perfectionism perception and contextual performance. In line with the findings, H₅ is accepted.

Table 19. The Effect of Socially Oriented Perfectionism Perception on Task Performance Level

Variable	B	Standard Error	β	t	Sig.
Fixed	2,526	0,153	-	16,462	0,000*
Socially Oriented Perfectionism	0,460	0,042	0,483	10,896	0,000*

*p<0.05

Adjusted R² =0.231;

Durbin Watson= 2,034

Source: Elaborated by Authors

When the assumptions of regression analysis are analyzed, it is seen that socially oriented perfectionism perception is effective on task performance. Within the findings obtained, it was determined that the perception of socially oriented perfectionism explained 23.1% of the change in task performance level (adjusted R² =0.231). According to the standardized regression coefficient (β), there is a positive and significant ($\beta=0.483$, p=0.000 p<0.05) relationship between socially oriented perfectionism perception and task performance. In line with the findings, H₆ is accepted.

7. Conclusions

This study aims to examine the effect of perfectionism perceptions of the employees of four and five star hotel establishments operating in Izmir city center on their job performance.

According to the results of the analysis, when the distribution of the findings regarding the demographic characteristics of the employees is analyzed according to gender, it is seen that there are more male employees, and according to marital status; there are more single employees. According to these findings, it is thought that the reasons such as the fact that the tourism sector is a labor-intensive sector, the working hours are long and the working conditions are intense, and individuals cannot spare time for their families and themselves due to long working hours are effective in the high number of male and single employees. When the average age of the participants is examined, it is seen that the majority of the employees are between the ages of 21-30 and 31-40, and according to their educational background, the majority of them are undergraduate graduates. According to the distribution of income status; it is seen that the majority have an income of 4000 TL and above and 3001-4000 TL. According to this result, it is possible to say that hotel businesses prefer young, dynamic and well-educated individuals due to the characteristics of the tourism sector such as being labor-intensive due to its reliance on manpower, being a sector that produces services, production and consumption taking place simultaneously in front of the customer and customer satisfaction being of great importance.

Within the scope of the research, when the participants' length of service in the sector is analyzed, it is seen that the majority of them have been working in the sector for 10 years or more and 1-3 years. According to these findings, it is thought that the reasons such as the challenging working conditions of the tourism sector, intensive working hours and diversity of working hours, and being negatively affected by negative political, economic and cultural events cause individuals not to continue in the tourism sector in a stable manner. According to the findings regarding the

duration of the participants' employment in the hotel, it is seen that the majority of the employees have been working in the business between 1-3 years. It is possible to attribute this result to the seasonal nature of the tourism sector, the insufficiency of the wages received by the employees, the inappropriate working conditions and the high employee turnover rate. When the distribution of the employees participating in the research is analyzed according to their education in the field of tourism, it is concluded that there are more people with tourism education, and when the distribution is analyzed according to the department they work in, it is concluded that the majority work in the food and beverage department, front office and housekeeping departments respectively. Considering that the majority of the time of the customers in hotel establishments is spent in the services offered by the food and beverage department, the fact that the food and beverage department has the highest number of employees, that this department has a great importance in influencing the customer's hotel preference and that it contributes greatly to the total income, these factors support the result obtained. When the result of the front office department is considered, the fact that hotel customers first encounter the front office department when they enter the hotel and thus have an impact on the first impression of the customer about the hotel, that it is a department that requires long hours of standing work and has a large number of employees due to its characteristics such as shift working hours supports the result obtained. In addition, it can be said that it is important that the employees in this department are always vigorous, dynamic, careful and trained in the field.

According to the results of the study, when the answers of the employees to the questions on perfectionism perception and job performance were analyzed, it was found that their perfectionism perception was at a high level (3.60). When the averages of the sub-dimensions of perfectionism were analyzed, it was determined that the perception of perfectionism towards themselves was at a high level (3,85), perfectionism towards others was at a medium level (3,38) and socially oriented perfectionism was at a high level (3,50). According to this result, it can be said that hotel employees set high standards for themselves rather than others and make great efforts to achieve these standards.

According to the results of the research; when the answers of the employees regarding the job performance variable were analyzed, it was determined that the levels of general job performance (4.10), task performance (4.13) and contextual performance (4.08) were high. When the dimension averages of the job performance scale are evaluated, it is seen that employees fulfill both their jobs, which are

their basic duties, and activities outside their basic duties, such as helping their colleagues and volunteering in other jobs. However, the analysis shows that the mean of task performance (4.13) is higher than the mean of contextual performance (4.08). In this direction, it is thought that employees with high performance are those who show more expertise related to the job. Since the tourism sector is labor-intensive and the manpower factor is important, employees should work with the expertise required by their profession and successfully fulfill the assigned tasks.

In the study, it was found that there is a moderate and positive relationship between employees' general perfectionism perceptions and their general job performance. This result shows that the two variables change together. In other words, perfectionism perception and job performance level increase or decrease together. In this context, it can be said that positive developments in employees' perceptions of perfectionism can be reflected on their job performance, and positive developments in job performance will have an impact on their perceptions of perfectionism. Since the quality of the service provided by employees with increased job performance levels will increase, customer satisfaction of the business will increase and will contribute positively to the profitability of the business. In the study conducted by Balçioğlu (2019) on public managers, it was determined that there is a significant positive relationship between perceived level of perfectionism and general performance. Hrabluik, Latham, and McCarthy (2012), on the other hand, concluded that performance and general perfectionism are negatively related in their study on a sample of police officers.

There is a moderate and positive relationship between perfectionism perception and job performance sub-dimensions of task performance and contextual performance. In line with this result, it is thought that positive developments in employees' perfectionism levels will positively affect their job performance. Positive developments in employees' level of perfectionism both increase their contribution to the technical power of the business and have a positive effect on the productivity of the business as a result of their voluntary participation in activities that are not included in the job description, cooperation with their colleagues and adoption of organizational goals. Günyaktı (2021) examined the effect of congruent and incongruent perfectionism perceptions of 347 white-collar employees working in different sectors on task performance and concluded that the effect of employees' congruent perfectionism perceptions on task performance is significant and positive (Günyaktı, 2021). Similarly, Stoll et al. (2008) found that there is a

positive relationship between perfectionism perceptions of athletes and their performance. Therefore, the results of this study are in parallel with the results obtained by Günyaktı (2021) and Stoll et al. (2008). According to this result, besides the limited number of studies examining the relationship between perfectionism and job performance in the tourism literature, there are studies in different fields that aim to determine the relationship between perfectionism and task performance. This result in different sectors is in parallel with the result in the service sector.

There is a high level and positively significant relationship between the level of self-oriented perfectionism, which is one of the sub-dimensions of perfectionism variable, and contextual performance and task performance, which are sub-dimensions of job performance. The fact that the employees get more efficiency from their work by working in cooperation with their colleagues and volunteering in other jobs, setting high standards for themselves and making great efforts to reach the high standards they set enables them to be appreciated and accepted as successful by the senior management. Therefore, it can be said that the contextual performance of appreciated and successful employees is also positively affected. However, it is possible that employees who set high standards that are difficult to reach and fail to reach these standards may become anxious and make mistakes, which may have a negative impact on themselves and their coworkers. Examples of these negative effects are job stress, disengagement, absenteeism and anger. On the other hand, as the perfectionism levels of employees who set high standards for themselves increase, their task performance also increases. This result can be explained by the fact that employees show more performance to reach the high standards they set. It can be said that individuals who are highly motivated for success and who avoid making mistakes perform more efficiently and effectively, enabling the organization to achieve its goals. Kobori and Tanno (2005), who examined the negative and positive aspects of self-oriented perfectionism, observed that individuals with high self-oriented perfectionism set very high standards for themselves, first make mistakes and their performance is negatively affected, but then they overcome their failures and the performance of perfectionists is positively affected.

There is a low level, positive and significant relationship between the level of perfectionism towards others, which is one of the sub-dimensions of perfectionism variable, and contextual performance and task performance, which are sub-dimensions of job performance. The relationship between employees and departments is very important for ensuring customer satisfaction and high service quality in hotel

businesses. One of the factors affecting the relationship between employees and each other is their personality traits. The perception of perfectionism towards others, which is a sub-dimension of the perfectionism factor, which is accepted as a personality trait, includes the individuals working in the business expecting high standards that are difficult to achieve from other employees and expecting the performance to be perfect. It is possible that as the employees' expectations of high performance from other employees, their belief in their success and their sense of trust in them increase, their tendency to cooperate, to help each other, to do other jobs voluntarily increases and to motivate each other. If the employees working in cooperation are motivated, it is possible to increase the productivity of the enterprise by performing their activities in accordance with their purpose. Therefore, it is possible to say that as the perfectionism perceptions of the employees towards others increase, the levels of contextual performance and task performance also increase, albeit slightly. It is thought that the reason for the low level of this effect is explained by the fact that hotel businesses are operated according to a certain regulation and rule.

There is a moderate, positive and significant relationship between the level of socially oriented perfectionism, which is one of the sub-dimensions of perfectionism variable, and contextual performance and task performance, which are sub-dimensions of job performance. Employees' belief that other people expect them to achieve perfection affects their performance. Positive evaluation and appreciation of the work done by others increases the morale and motivation of employees, enabling them to cooperate with their colleagues, to volunteer in jobs that are not included in the job description, to support in improving organizational processes, to increase their commitment to work, and to successfully fulfill the assigned tasks by using their professional knowledge and skills. In Flett, Greene, and Hewitt's (2004) study examining the relationship between the dimensions of perfectionism and anxiety level, they concluded that socially oriented perfectionist individuals show negative contextual performance behaviors along with behaviors such as not being open to evaluation and criticism by other employees, reacting and being anxious (Flett, Greene, & Hewitt, 2004). In a study conducted by Lee, Ha, and Jue (2019) on students, it was observed that the perception of socially oriented perfectionism has negative effects such as depression, anxiety, and inadequacy in individuals (Lee, Haa, & Jue, 2019).

This study, which examines the effect of perfectionism perception on job performance, was conducted on four and five star hotel employees operating in Izmir city center. The limitations of the research are that the

research data were obtained from a single city and four and five star hotels using convenience sampling method. Therefore, the generalizability of the research is limited. Future similar studies can be designed in subgroups of the tourism sector, such as travel businesses, food and beverage businesses, airline businesses, etc. and with larger sample groups, or a similar study can be designed on employees in different hotel segments and comparisons can be made according to hotel types. In this way, it may be possible to generalize the results of the research.

In addition, it is recommended to utilize the evaluations of managers, coworkers or customers when evaluating the performance of employees, and to utilize interview as a data collection method and 360-degree appraisal method to obtain more objective and in-depth data. In this study, which shows that perfectionism has a positive effect on job performance, perfectionism was used as an independent variable and job performance as a dependent variable. It may be suggested that future studies should examine the relationships between work performance and a different independent variable such as workaholism, job burnout and self-efficacy without depending on the perfectionism variable. It is also possible to examine the relationships between other personality traits such as agreeableness, conscientiousness and extraversion and job performance.

In addition to the academic suggestions based on the research limitations, managerial suggestions are also presented in line with the research results. Performance studies conducted in businesses are determined according to the personality traits of employees. It can be said that the implementation of appreciation and rewarding systems by taking into account the personality traits of employees will prevent the negative effects that employees will face at work. In cases where perfectionism negatively affects the performance of employees, managers should focus on the problem and make efforts to solve the problem. Managers should develop policies that will motivate employees, increase their organizational commitment and positively affect their performance. Employees with increased commitment to work, strong inter-employee relations and high performance will be effective in increasing the profitability and service quality of the organization.

It would be useful to provide training and seminars for managers to get to know their employees better, to set standards appropriate to their personality traits and to make healthier decisions. In addition, employing psychological experts to solve the problems encountered in businesses will have positive effects on the business and employees. The fact that managers know the personality traits of their subordinates, work

in cooperation, and that employees know each other's personality traits and cooperate with each other will ensure the continuity of the work and positively affect the task performance and contextual performance of the employees. If managers act in this direction, in the long run, employees with high job performance will contribute to the increase in tourists' interest in hotels and destinations thanks to the excellent services offered by hotel businesses.

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